

TABLE I

Compound	Colour	Transition (t) or decom. (d) temperature °C	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)			
			C	H	N	M
Mg(8HQ) ₂ Br ₄ =L	Yellow	238 d				
L ₂ Py	Dirty white	165 t	41.87 (42.59)	2.67 (2.98)	6.86 (7.08)	3.00 (3.09)
L ₂ H ₂ O	Yellowish green	140 t	31.78 (32.33)	2.23 (2.30)	3.97 (4.19)	3.38 (3.59)
L ₂ en	Yellow	202 t	33.92 (34.68)	2.65 (2.89)	7.89 (8.09)	3.29 (3.46)
L ₂ 1N2N	Light green	255 d	41.38 (41.79)	2.09 (2.23)	5.10 (5.22)	2.78 (2.98)
L ₂ ONP	Yellow	170 t	36.92 (37.40)	2.00 (2.07)	5.32 (5.45)	3.01 (3.11)
L ₂ SalH	Deep yellow	204 d	39.07 (39.84)	2.17 (2.25)	3.57 (3.71)	3.00 (3.18)
L ₂ Catechol	Yellowish green	185 t	38.22 (38.81)	2.28 (2.42)	3.51 (3.77)	3.09 (3.23)
L ₂ gl	Greenish yellow	202 t	33.89 (34.58)	2.38 (2.59)	3.97 (4.03)	3.21 (3.45)
L ₂ <i>o</i> -phen.	Ash	170 t	38.26 (38.91)	2.51 (2.70)	7.32 (7.56)	3.08 (3.24)
L ₂ AnthA	Brown	150 t	38.69 (39.06)	2.18 (2.34)	5.32 (5.46)	2.98 (3.12)

Py=pyridine; en=ethylenediamine; 1N2N=1-nitroso-2-naphthol; ONP=*o*-nitrophenol; SalH=salicylaldehyde; gl=ethyleneglycol; *o*-phen=*o*-phenylenediamine; AnthA=anthranilic acid.

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cobalt(II) Containing N-Allyl Thiourea and Nitrogen Donor Atoms: Penta and Hexa Coordinated

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SEVERAL mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II) with thiourea, allyl thiourea, diphenyl thiourea, N-methyl thiourea, N,N-dimethyl thiourea etc., have been reported earlier¹⁻⁴. It was thought worthwhile to undertake the study of the complexes of cobalt(II) perchlorate with N-allyl thiourea and morpholine and 1,10-phenanthroline.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by the direct addition of cobalt(II) perchlorate, N-allyl thiourea and morpholine or 1,10-phenanthroline in 1:2:2 ratio in methanol followed by the addition of ether

and then crystallisation from hot methanol and final drying *in vacuo*.

Elemental analysis (Table I) carried out by standard methods were consistent with the formulations of the compounds. Conductance measurements were carried out in 10⁻³ M acetone solution using Toshniwal conductivity bridge, type CL 0102 with a dip type cell. The magnetic susceptibilities were determined using Gouy method. Infrared spectra were recorded in the region 4000-400 cm⁻¹ by Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra were recorded by Elico model CD24 spectrophotometer. These data are given in Table I.

Results and Discussion

The molar conductance values for the compounds, $\Lambda_M = 153$ and 242 mhos cm² mole⁻¹, indicate 1:1 and 1:2 electrolytes, respectively. The values have been calculated on the basis of the formula weight. The magnetic susceptibility measurements indicate that both the complexes are paramagnetic. For the first compound $\nu(\text{Cl}-\text{O})$ was observed as two sharp bands at 930 and 620 cm⁻¹ indicating that one of the perchlorate groups is coordinated to the metal ion (620 cm⁻¹) while the other is free (ionic) (930 cm⁻¹)⁵⁻⁸. But in case of the second compound, $\nu(\text{Cl}-\text{O})$ was observed as a single band at 1090 cm⁻¹ indicating that both the perchlorate groups are ionic and not coordinated to metal ion.

Comparison of the ir spectrum of the N-allyl thiourea with those of the complexes shows a -ve shift of the order of 200 cm⁻¹ in NH stretching frequency, suggesting coordination through nitrogen⁷. Again, the bands due to thiomide I [$\nu(\text{C}=\text{S}) + \nu(\text{C}-\text{N})$] and thiomide II [$\delta(\text{CH}) + \delta(\text{NH}) +$

TABLE I—ANALYSIS, CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITIES DATA

Compound	m.p. °C	%CO	%Halogen	%S	%N	%C	%H	ΔM (mhos)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
[Co(NATU) ₂ (Moph) ₂ ClO ₄] ₂ ClO ₄	>300	8.72 (8.87)*	10.56 (10.68)	9.48 (9.62)	12.51 (12.65)	28.68 (28.90)	5.00 (5.14)	153	4.84
[Co(NATU) ₂ (phen) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	>300	6.85 (6.93)	8.25 (8.34)	7.34 (7.52)	13.00 (13.17)	44.88 (45.16)	4.92 (5.08)	242	4.96

* Figures in parenthesis indicate calculated values.

$\nu(\text{CN})$] at 1445 and 1330 cm^{-1} and thionide III [$\nu(\text{CS}) + \nu(\text{CN})$] and [$\nu(\text{C}=\text{S}) + \delta(\text{NCS})$] at 935 and 1245 cm^{-1} show a +ve shift, clearly indicating coordination through nitrogen of N-allyl thiourea⁸.

The bands at 3210 and 1100 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C})$ stretch respectively clearly indicated that one morpholine coordinated through nitrogen and the other through oxygen atom⁹. The band¹⁰ at 1430 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ and the bands¹¹ at 840 and 720 cm^{-1} due to C-H out of plane bending vibrations and ring stretching of 1,10-phenanthroline clearly indicated that 1,10-phenanthroline coordinated through both the nitrogen atoms.

In the electronic spectra of phenanthroline complex the bands at ~ 500 , ~ 600 and at 850 nm are assignable to ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ (ν_3), ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}(\text{F})$ (ν_2) and ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ (ν_1) indicating the octahedral structure¹¹. For the other complex the bands at 515 (ν_4), 665 (ν_2) and 870 nm (ν_2) values suggest the complex to be penta-coordinated^{12,13}.

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Stabilities and Thermodynamics of Uranyl(II) and Thorium(IV) Complexes of DL-nor-Leucine

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IN continuation of our earlier investigations on the electrochemical behaviour of amino acids and their metal complexes¹⁻⁴, this communication deals with the study of the composition, stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} complexes with DL-nor-leucine for which no reference could be traced in literature.

Experimental

DL-nor-leucine (referred herein as HA) was supplied by B.D.H., Poole, England. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. pH measurements were made on a Toshniwal digital pH-meter with glass-calomel electrode assembly. Conductance was measured on an electronic type conductometer. Temperature was controlled by a universal (U_g -type) thermostat.

pH titrations were carried out in the absence and presence of metal ion against standard (0.1 M) NaOH for establishing the stoichiometry of the complexes formed during the interaction of metal ion and HA. For determining stability constants at 20, 30 and 40°, the ratio of metal to ligand was always one to five (1:5) and 5 mM HClO_4 was used for initial lowering of buffer region. The entire study was carried out in aqueous media at ionic strength of 0.1 M NaClO_4 . Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum method was applied to calculate the stability constants of the complexes formed.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: The composition of the complexes formed during the interaction of UO_2^{2+} and Th^{4+} with DL-nor-leucine was established by measuring the magnitude of the proton displacement during the titration of the ligand in absence and presence of metal ion in different molar ratios against standard NaOH.

The addition of an equimolar concentration of UO_2^{2+} greatly alters the shape of free-ligand titra-